

Symptoms and plant height reduction at 3 WAI, and grain yield reduction in plants of 6 cultivars infected at 1 wk after soaking, with RTBV + RTSV, RTBV alone, or RTSV alone. IRRI, 1988.

Cultivar	Virus	Symptoms ^a	Height reduction (%)	Yield reduction (%)
Balimau Putih	RTBV + RTSV	-	9.2	19.9
	RTBV	-	3.3	17.1
	RTSV	-	1.5	7.2
BW272-6B	RTBV + RTSV	S, Y, D	62.6	94.2
	RTBV	S, Y	59.4	81.9
	RTSV	-	16.3	14.5
FK135	RTBV + RTSV	S, Y, I, D	72.0	99.0
	RTBV	S, Y, I, D	68.2	98.0
	RTSV	-	2.9	19.5
Palasithari	RTBV + RTSV	S, Y, I	36.9	33.5
	RTBV	S, Y	34.6	20.6
	RTSV	-	4.5	10.1
Sigadis	RTBV + RTSV	S, Y, I	16.9	30.7
	RTBV	-	13.5	23.9
	RTSV	-	11.2	9.1
Utri Rajapan	RTBV + RTSV	s, t	29.4	28.8
	RTBV	-	21.8	16.8
	RTSV	-	2.3	1.6
TNI	RTBV + RTSV	S, Y, I	71.8	97.4
	RTBV	S, Y, I	49.1	94.7
	RTSV	-	3.7	19.5

^aS = severe stunting, s = mild stunting, Y = yellow orange discoloration, y = mild yellowing, I = inter-veinal chlorosis, D = drooping of leaves, t = reduced tillering, - (dash) = no clear symptoms.

Frequency distribution of infection rates and scores of 1,117 rice germplasm tested by the modified mass screening method. IRRI, 1988.

Using these results, we modified the greenhouse mass screening method as follows:

1. Seed 20 germinated seeds of each entry in a pot.
2. Allow vector leafhoppers (GLH) to feed 3-4 d on RTV-infected plants.
3. Confine 7- to 10-d-old seedlings of 16 entries in a cage with 8-10 viruliferous GLH/ seedling for 3 h.
4. Consecutively inoculate 2 additional sets of entries.
5. Allow the viruliferous GLH to feed overnight on RTV-infected plants,

then use them again for inoculation.

6. Score seedlings individually 3-4 WAI.

Score symptom severity as follows:

- 1 = no symptoms
 - 3 = 1-10% plant height reduction with no leaf discoloration
 - 5 = 11-30% plant height reduction with no distinct leaf discoloration
 - 7 = 31-50% plant height reduction and/ or yellow to orange leaf discoloration
 - 9 = more than 50% plant height reduction and yellow to orange leaf discoloration
7. Compute average score.
 8. Select all entries for which average score is lower than 4 and index plants in ELISA for presence of RTBV and RTSV.

Cultivars with scores lower than 3 were considered resistant (or tolerant); cultivars with scores of 5, moderately resistant. We tested more than 1,000 rice germplasm using this modified mass screening method. Nine percent had

scores 0-3 (see figure). Tjempo Kijik (Acc. no. 16602) and Utri Merah (Acc. no. 16682) exhibited very mild symptoms but had high infection with RTBV and/or RTSV. □

Reaction of rice to yellow dwarf disease (YDD) and green leafhopper (GLH)

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To identify sources of resistance to YDD and its GLH vector *Nephotettix virescens*, seedlings of 35 rice varieties were inoculated by 5 YDD-viruliferous leafhoppers per plant for 24 h. The varieties also were tested against GLH, using the standard bulk seedling damage rating test.

Popular local rice varieties showed high susceptibility to the YDD pathogen (41.7-100% infection). NLR139-69, RP1931-54, and Tadukan had no infection. RP1931-54 and Tadukan also were resistant to GLH. NLR139-69 was resistant to YDD infection but susceptible to GLH. Kalinga-1 showed high resistance to GLH but 25% YDD infection. IR20, IR50, and TKM6 were resistant to GLH but showed 83, 67, and 58% YDD infection, respectively. □

Genetic analysis of bacterial blight (BB) resistance in Madhya Pradesh, India

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We evaluated about 7,000 rice accessions being maintained at Zonal Rice Research Station, Raipur, for field resistance to BB in 1982, when BB natural infection was very severe. The 204 entries found to be relatively free of disease were tested for resistance to 4 Philippine races of BB at Los Baños in